

Effect of age (20, 40, 60 days) and number of seedlings per hill on grain yield of rice varieties, 1977 wet season, Pantnagar, India.

Seedlings (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)					
	Jaya			Pusa 2-21		
	20 d	40 d	60 d	20 d	40 d	60 d
2	6.8	6.5	4.9	7.3	6.0	4.6
4	7.5	5.7	5.7	7.3	6.2	5.2
6	7.4	6.6	5.0	7.4	6.7	5.4

Source of variation	Standard deviation of mean (±)	Coefficient of variation (%)	Coefficient of difference at 5%
Variety	0.3	19	
Seedling age	0.4		1.1
Seedlings/hill	0.4		1.1
Variety × age × seedlings/hill interaction	1.0		2.7

seedling number. The yield increased when the number of seedlings from the same age group rose from 2 to 6/hill (see table). The magnitude of yield reduction due to overaged seedlings was low for the medium-duration Jaya. The yield

increased with 2 and 4 seedlings of the same age group per hill, and 6 seedlings/hill for 40-day-old seedlings. The difference was probably due to a buildup in the insect population in a few plots. ■

Reduction of nursery area in wet cultivation of rice

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A study was conducted at Ambasamudram to determine the minimum area required for a seedbed and the optimum seeding rate.

Seedlings from the nursery seeded at 3, 6, and 9 kg/40 m² were healthier and stronger than those seeded at 12 kg/40 m². The seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m² were taller than those seeded at the other rates. The number of leaves that each seedling produced did not differ among

the various treatments (see table).

When the seed rate was increased from 3 to 6 kg/40 m², the number of seedlings per unit area proportionally increased. When the seed rate was increased to 9 and 12 kg/40 m² the increase in the number of seedlings was not proportional. That might be attributable to the high mortality of seedlings at higher seed rates.

The seedlings from the nursery seeded at 6 kg/40 m², when spaced at 20 × 10 cm, covered twice the main field area covered by the seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m². Increasing the seeding rate to 9 and 12 kg/40 m² did not result in a proportional increase in the main field area covered.

Effect of nursery seeding rate on rice seedlings and wet cultivation of rice, Paddy Experiment Station, Tamil Nadu, India.

Seeding rate (kg/40 m ²)	Seedling ht (cm)	Leaves (no./seedling)	Seedlings (no./m ²)	Area (m ²) covered in the main field with seedlings	Seedbed required to transplant 1 ha main field (m ²)	Transplanting rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
3	30	4	3201	21	480	36	6.2
6	23	4	6024	40	252	38	5.6
9	22	4	6816	45	224	51	5.2
12	22	4	8027	53	188	57	4.9

C.D.: 0.4

However, the yield of seedlings seeded at 6 kg/40 m² was lower (5.6 t/ha) than that of seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m² (6.2 t/ha) (see table). Because yield was the ultimate deciding factor, the nursery seeded at 3 kg/40 m² was the most economically advantageous. ■

Response of transplanted rice to zinc application in Gangetic alluvial soils

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Improved rice varieties planted in alluvial soils often show symptoms of zinc deficiency, particularly during early growth. Zinc deficiency is usually corrected by applying zinc to the soil or as a foliar spray. Therefore, to determine the importance of zinc application to rice production, an experiment was conducted with and without zinc. The zinc was applied at a rate of 16 kg/ha as soil application and 5 kg/ha as a foliar spray in kharif 1976 at the BHU Research Farm. The soil is medium-textured with a pH of 7.3.

Zinc as zinc sulfate was incorporated into the soil at final puddling; it was also sprayed at the tillering and booting growth stages. The effects of the two methods of zinc application on plant height, straw yield, and grain yield components were compared.

The experiment showed that alluvial soils are deficient in available zinc. Zinc application increased grain and straw yield significantly. Foliar-sprayed zinc increased yield by 17.2%; it also increased straw yield and 100-grain weight. Both soil and foliar application of zinc significantly affected plant height and number of grains per panicle. ■

Nitrogen management at moderate levels of nitrogen in lowland rice

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A field experiment on nitrogen

management was conducted with transplanted Jaya rice on Tarai soil in the lowlands of Uttar Pradesh, India, during the 1977-78 wet season. Total nitrogen used was 60 kg/ha as ordinary urea, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea-enriched farmyard manure (FYM), urea incubated with soil, and pellet application of urea incubated with soil. Single superphosphate and muriate of potash at 40 kg P₂O₅/ha and 25 kg K₂O/ha were basally applied to all plots.

Differences in grain yield due to source and timing of N application were significant. Nitrogen use was most efficient with SCU broadcast as a single application and incorporated into the soil before transplanting (see table).

Effect of timing of application and source of nitrogen (N) on grain yield of rice. Pantnagar, India.

Planting	N application (kg/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)
	Early tillering	Late tillering	Panicle initiation	
0	0	0	0	4.9
60	0	0	0	6.4
15	15	15	15	6.9
0	30	0	30	6.4
0	20	20	20	6.5
30 ^a	15 ^a	0	15 ^a	6.5
30 ^b	15 ^b	0	15 ^b	6.4
60 ^c	0	0	0	7.1
30 ^c	15	0	15	7.0
30 ^d	15 ^d	0	15 ^d	6.3

S.E m± 0.2

CD at 5% 0.6

CV (%) 7

^a Urea incubated with soil. ^b Pellet application of urea incubated with soil. ^c Sulfur-coated urea.

^d Urea-enriched farmyard manure.

Fertilizer and weed management of aus rice in Bangladesh

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Inadequate weed and fertilizer management hampers aus (monsoon) rice production in Bangladesh.

A 1979 experiment in the BRRI

project area used the improved variety Chandina under farmer conditions to determine: 1) the yield gap between the potential and the farmer's actual yields, 2) the effectiveness of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control on yield, and 3) the economics of alternative practices. The design was complete factorial in a randomized complete block, with three applications, each with nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control. The crops were grown with supplementary irrigation.

Yield with the farmer's practices (2.6 t/ha) and potential yield (4.3 t/ha) showed a gap of 1.7 t/ha (see table). The use of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control bridged the gap by 0.7, 0.6, and 0.7 t/ha, respectively. The change brought in a net income of US\$415/ha. The benefit-cost ratio for the extra investment ranged from 5.3 to 16.4, depending on the treatment combinations. ■

Agroeconomics of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed management over farmer's levels in BRRI cropping systems research site at Salna, Bangladesh, 1979 aus.

Treatment ^a			Av yield (t/ha)	Yield difference from farmers' level (kg/ha)	Value of yield difference (US\$/ha)	Cost of H inputs (US\$/ha)	Added profit over farmer's treatment (US\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Nitrogen	Sulfur	Weeding frequency						
F(54 kg/ha)	F(0)	F(zero)	2.6	—	—	—	—	—
F	F	H(3)	3.0	401	106.93	7.87	99.06	12.6
F	H(34 kg/ha)	F	3.1	440	117.33	14.53	102.80	7.1
F	H	H	3.2	532	141.86	22.40	119.47	5.3
H(80 kg/ha)	F	F	3.1	453	120.80	7.20	113.60	15.8
H	F	H	3.3	686	182.93	15.07	167.87	11.1
H	H	F	4.1	1419	378.40	21.73	356.67	16.4
H	H	H	4.3	1669	445.06	29.60	415.47	14.0

^a F = farmer's level of management (traditional system), H = improved management (improved variety).

Modified urea materials and nitrogen efficiency in wetland rice

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The growth and yield of wetland rice

depend on the availability and use of nitrogen at the various physiological stages of the crop. Split application, placement, and controlled release are the three major approaches to increasing nitrogen efficiency in wetland rice. Five seasons of experimentation at Mandya have shown that the basal application of nitrogen in mudballs, paper capsules, and

as supergranules and sulfur-coated urea is superior to split application.

In a replicated trial conducted in the summer of 1979 under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), basal application of several modified urea materials was compared with basal and split applications of prilled urea. Granulated compost and super-